

Analysis of Vulnerability Factors of NGOs: An Interpretive Structural Modeling (ISM) Approach

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Abstract

Non-governmental organizations work for the welfare of society as well as contribute to the economic development of a country. As non-governmental organizations face serious performance declines since last decade around the world, not only in specific geographic area, there is a dire need for exploring the cause of such decline in order to fight the issue in time. In lieu of this, this study is an effort to reach to the susceptibility factors that are the reasons for declining performance of non-governmental organizations in the context of Pakistan. Seven susceptible factors have been identified from literature and expert's opinion which were further categorized into twenty-two sub-factors in order to deal with the issue of declining performance of non-governmental organizations in greater detail. The *twelve* members' panel of experts is recruited to collect data. The qualitative data required for this study is collected through a comprehensive review of the literature and from tacit knowledge of experts having at least 10 years' experience and belonging directly/indirectly to different NGOs, Government departments, universities professors and other stakeholders who are the beneficiaries of NGOs. This is an exploratory study based on survey. The Interpretive Structural Modeling (ISM) is used to recognize and categorize susceptible performance factors and create a structural/hierarchical model to understand interrelationships among these susceptibility factors. The factors of teamwork, funding, donations, rules & regulations and recruitment fall at *level I*. Recruitment and rules & regulations on *level I* of ISM model signifies the importance of dimension of HR Practices. On *level II*, the presence of organizational structure and budget indicate the importance of proper structure and funding for NGOs' sustainability. On *level III*, the factor of proactive approach is present. *Level IV* represents factors of executive body, employee engagement, workload and turnover rate. *Level V* represents factors of politics, responsibility, employee motivation and teamwork whereas *level VI* represents factors of appreciation rewards. *Level VII* represents employee honesty and *level VIII* represents employee behavior respectively. *Level IX* represents training & development whereas *level X* represents advance & latest technology and technology experts. Cross Impact Matrix Multiplication Applied to Classification (MICMAC) is used to classify variables along two dimensions; their driving power and dependence power. MICMAC enhances the reliability and validity of the ISM model. It groups variables as autonomous, independent, dependent and linkage variables. MICMAC presented Employee Engagement (C16) as a dependent and Executive Body (C8) as an independent variables. The rest of the variables appeared as autonomous variables. This study intends to contribute towards theoretical as well as practical implication for a broad range of stakeholders including, the administrators of NGOs, the Government, the beneficiaries, and the society.

Keywords: NGOs', Declining Performance, Susceptibility Factors, Sustainable development, ISM

1. Introduction

Self-governing organizations without the involvement of Government are known as non-governmental organizations (NGOs). The NGOs are established by an individual, group of individuals or subgroup of societies for the welfare of the same. The NGOs' objective is to help and sustain less privileged individuals/groups/societies to create a positive impact on individual/ groups/societies as well as to contribute towards economic growth & development of a country. About 100,000 to 150,000 social welfare organizations are currently working in Pakistan. The last decade has witnessed downward sloping performance of NGOs. The available literature is silent on study of susceptible factors that lead to performance issue of NGOs particularly social NGOs. Typically, NGOs face various challenges related to Power, Technology, Management, Finance, HR Practices, Remuneration and Organizational Commitment. Therefore, in lieu of this, there is a dire need to focus on these abovementioned challenges. Majority of the NGOs depend on external funding, government funds, donations, community contributors, membership fee and grants for delivery of good cause (Barczak et al., 2006). Among the funding sources of NGOs, donations are the proactive strategy for NGOs' survival. Donor societies and development agencies are the essential part of international development to mobilize the peoples' life (Okada, 2013). Firms use proactive approach as charitable donations to decrease the negative impact of environmental misconduct through SMEs to protect their market image (Wu et al., 2020). Garcia et al., (2019) asserted to increase the transparency tasks with the help of frontier items to connect functions and settle the official planning. Since employees' success is positively correlated with organizational rewards, therefore, the central importance in every organization is to structure the incentive system (Liu and Stuart, 2014).

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Jordan & Tuijl (2000) revealed that NGO networks are highly complex affected by political forces; particularly, the dictatorship regimes ignore human rights and peoples' problems and demands are not considered significant (Audi & Ali, 2019; Henriquez & Venegas, 2020).

Entrepreneurs are interested in investment opportunities that promote innovations through advance technologies. The goal behind this drive is a cost-effective program that can achieve economies of scale and provide highly skilled technology experts to industries (Smith & Louwagie, 2017; Audi & Ali, 2017). Opportunities are sources to motivate entrepreneurs who operate in countries may still be prepared to use the modern technologies to generate new enterprise innovations (Mohsen et al., 2020). However, the developed and independent nations are relatively free from political influence (Fukumoto et al., 2020; Ali, 2022). The Executive officers have leadership qualities i-e, vision, team orientation & management, coordination, and entrepreneurial motivation that are necessary to gear up the company towards success. Majority of the NGOs are working on the basis of internal rules and regulations. Ghasemi et al., (2020) assessed organization performance and suggested improvements in procedures, financial management, regulation of donations and volunteering. Strategic HRM is a successful business strategy and provides road map for attracting highly compatible and quality employees (Belinda et al., 2018; Ali, 2022). Further, training sessions help detect mental stress and depression of employees (Lin et al., 2020). Leaders' intelligence and employee engagement both are highly positive correlated for creativity and innovation. HR practices help to enhance enthusiasm that enables employees for longer work engagement (Katou et al., 2020). The burden of work at workplace leads to various employees' issues e.g., fatigue, absenteeism job dissatisfaction, low productivity and high turnover etc. Price (1995) elaborated that employee turnover and employee absenteeism are critical to organizational performance. Employee commitment and turnover intention are strongly and negatively correlated (Lyons & Bandura, 2021). The person organization fit refers to attraction selection attrition (ASA) theory that employees love to work in that organization which are matched to their personality and behaviors (Schneider, 1987). Latif & William (2017) asserted that team leader is responsible for the performance of the whole team. The critical attributes of teamwork are co-ordination, social linkage, combined performance, skills and knowledge, leadership qualities, commitment, judgmental thinking and sharing. The failure of projects is highly dependent on lack of team coordination and the lack of coordination/ cooperation among employees exists due to lack of trust (Dewi, Manochin, & Belal, 2019). Ignorance of the abovementioned dimensions and susceptibility factors lead to the NGOs face less productivity issues that ultimately lead to disappointment of stakeholders i-e, clients, donors and beneficiaries. Lack of funding is the most vulnerable challenge for NGOs. Majority NGOs obtain funds from a wide variety of sources to reduce the vulnerability to meet their social mission and organizational goals. There is a need to provide a framework for practitioners that can help them adopt pro-active approach and reinforce the need to understand vulnerable factors for the sustainable development of NGOs. To evaluate the importance and interrelationship among susceptible factors the classical method of ISM was used which has unique capabilities to convert mental knowledge into structural model to give understanding about factors' priority and inter-relationship between them. This study intends to be a founding stone upon which further studies related to sustainable development of NGOs can be based. The study has implications for a wide variety of stakeholders including the administrators of NGOs, the government, the donors, the volunteers and the society. To our knowledge, there has been no study of such type that explores/identifies susceptible factors and their inter relationship in the context of declined performance of NGOs.

2. Literature Review

The aim of NGOs is to provide services for human welfare and society's well-being. NGOs are established voluntarily and enjoy high level of control over their own accountability processes. They are not for private profit or gain. Every year more than 1000 NGOs are listed in the U.S. Bugalia, Maemura, & Ozawa, (2020) identified managerial and institutional elements disturbing high-speed rail safety of Japan that highlighted the safety issues. Berta, Ronelle, (2015) conducted research on NGOs of Uganda and suggested for further research on NGOs' vulnerability. The primary factors identified through content analysis of previous literature and refined through experts' opinion were further categorized into twenty-two susceptibility factors viz-a-viz, the Power factor into five, the Technology into two sub-factors, the Management into three, the Finance into three, the HR practices into three, Remuneration into three, and Organizational commitment into three sub factors. The study dimensions and sub-factors are briefly discussed below:

- a) **Power (B1):** The Government of any country has legitimate power to shape the NGOs. People usually prefer to not debate on power, however, there is no doubt that power can be acquired and exercised for vice purposes. McClelland's theory of need asserts that he need for power is the desire to influence another individuals' behavior as per wish. Relational theory of power defines a relationship of personal qualities that are important and valuable to others. Different facets of Power used in context of this study have been briefly explained here:

- i. **Proactive approach (C1):** It is very important to understand the power tactics. Role theory is a combination of standard norms, or concepts of a person (Biddle & Thomas, 1966). To obtain talent management outcomes, the proactive behavior of talented employees plays an important role (Meyers, 2020).
 - ii. **Responsibility (C2):** Garcia et al., (2019) offers a basic understanding of the role of determinants e.g., co-operation, harmonization, and communication skills to achieve successful initiatives.
 - iii. **Appreciation & Rewards (C3):** Rewards, incentives and monitoring schemes are the best ways to encourage employees to achieve organizational goals (Leete, 2000). The influence of chance on the performance of companies and managers, rewards is ever-present (Houdek, 2017).
 - iv. **Politics (C4):** Rosen and Hochwarter (2014) asserted that not everyone is affected equally by politics, few employees are less affected, and some are highly affected.
 - v. **Dictatorship (C5):** Foreign policy has been devoted to encourage dictatorship to become democratic (Mulligan, & Tsui, 2015).
- b) **Technology (B2):** Operations and policies of NGOs are based on government interventions to promote innovations in business sectors through advance technology (Mgumia, Mattee, & Kundi, 2015). Different facets of technology have been mentioned here:
- i. **Advance Technology (C6):** Technology innovation brings change in communication and productivity in the society. Almasi (2014) asserted that hi-tech technology has sufficient explanations, guidelines and latest technologies are accessible for special reason gear units.
 - ii. **Technology Experts (C7):** Previous research was directed to assess the routine of superior technology experts as older adults with an uttered high attention in technology innovations. Older adults showed their differences in terms of their technology acceptance, experiences, and assets.
- c) **Management (B3):** In reference to managerial challenges faced by NGOs, some are mentioned here –e-g, proper network is not operating, lack of supremacy; many NGOs do not have a panel & no strategic planning. Management dimension is also further classified into facets i-e, executive body, rules & regulations and organizational structure.
- i. **Executive Body (C8):** A successful organization is working with experts and board members. Executives' career and organizational outcomes are related to aesthetic attributes (Devine et. al., 2020).
 - ii. **Rules & Regulations (C9):** Employees gather information to solve specific problem through organizational systems and procedures (Caniels, 2019).
 - iii. **Organizational Structure (C10):** Organizational structure is a base to groundwork in which standard operating procedures (SOPs) and practices rest.
- d) **Finance (B4):** This is very difficult for NGOs to take up, initiate and carry on project due to limited fund available to them. One of the reasons could be the lack of co-operation between the Pakistani NGOs and the Government. The finance dimension has following sub-factors.
- i. **Budget (C11):** During 1980s' government grants declined dramatically. Abigail Payne (1997) asserted that during the ten-year period study, fixed effects do not control for time-varying changes at the non-profit level.
 - ii. **Funding (C12):** NGOs are continuously facing difficulties in obtaining funds. In the case of annual profits of corporations, NGOs do not have a straight forward baseline (Gray et al. 2006), to measure the performance of NGOs' there are some developed criteria.
 - iii. **Donations (C13):** Donors are a source of funding for NGOs. In the late 1990s', the donor funding has declined, donor priorities began to shift and foreign support budgets moved down.
- e) **HR Practices (B5):** NGOs are important for the welfare of the country and the human resource should be utilized properly (Tessema and Soeters, 2006). The dimension of HR Practices has following sub-factors.
- i. **Recruitment (C14):** Human resource department includes employee oriented activities such as recruitment, selection, training and growth, performance assessment, work surroundings, returns, rewards and contribution etc.
 - ii. **Training/Development (C15):** Virtual Training (VT) is used to develop the social skills, abilities, creativity, and current knowledge of employees (Howard, & Gutworth, 2020).
 - iii. **Employee Engagement (C16):** Professional identification of employees leads to higher employee engagement and reduced turnover (Wang et. al., 2020).
- f) **Remuneration (B6):** Management of the organizations should develop programs and policies to retention employees (Park & Min, 2020). The dimension of Remuneration has following sub-factors.
- i. **Workload (C17):** Howe (2005) asserted that in Australian workplaces, longer working hours was a reason of labor market deregulation.
 - ii. **Employee Motivation (C18):** Employee motivation is based on structure of wages and employer fairness in determination of wages (Leete, 2000).
 - iii. **Turnover Rate (C19):** Due to higher turnover rate, organizations face greater loss in productivity performance.

g) Organizational Commitment (B7): Employees' friendly environment is positively related to organization attractiveness and commitment (Kim, Kim, Han, Jackson, & Ployhart, 2017). The dimension of Organizational Commitment has following sub-factors.

i. Employee Behavior (C20): Maslow's Growth theory is a part of ERG Theory 1969. Behaviour of employees is dependent on organizational fairness in treating employees (Bateman & Organ, 1983).

ii. Teamwork (C21): To successfully complete projects, the role of teamwork is a significant attribute.

iii. Employee Honesty (C22): Projects require people to have features of caring, responsibility, honesty and hardworking (Latif & Williams, 2017).

This study is offers a framework for providing useful information to executives to take precautionary measures and convert weaknesses into strengths for the sustainable development of NGOs. The study reveals related information of social welfare sector in Pakistan which paves the way for further research. The summary of vulnerable factors and their dimensions in given Table 1.

Table 1: The Study Dimensions and Susceptibility Factors of (NGOs)

Dimensions	Factors	Description	Source
Power (B1)	Proactive Approach (C1)	An empirical study described that script proficiency increases by the proactive training.	(Nicod, Llosa, & Bowen 2020)
	Responsibility (C2)	For making organization socially responsible, individuals' perception of responsibility leads to positive image of organization success.	(Belinda et al., 2018)
	Appreciation/ Rewards (C3)	A study was conducted for the wellness of programs of various types of incentives like cash, gift cards and tangible rewards.	(Heninger et al., 2019)
	Politics (C4)	The term politics has been used to refer to unlawful, self-serving behavior designed to protect or enhance actors' self-interests.	(Chang, Rosen, & Levy, 2009)
	Dictatorship (C5)	Refers to judging the organization's benefits on one's personal position and not for the welfare of the organization.	(Vervimp, 2003)
Technology	Advanced & Latest Technology (C6)	Technology innovation brings change in communication productivity and performance of NGOs'.	(Mao et al., 2020)
	Technology Experts (C7)	Workers should literate or train employees for high-tech technology and latest equipment.	(Jokisch et al., 2020)
Management (B3)	Executive Body (C8)	NGOs' have a hierarchical structure. It clarify the importance of optimal use of resources and meeting the set goals.	(Ghasemi et. al., 2020)
	Rules & Regulations (C9)	Employees must follow the rules, regulations and procedures on workplace. Service rules & SOPs make employees responsible, active and obedient.	(Ozduran, & Tanova, 2017)
	Organizational Structure (C10)	Organizational structure disturbs organizational deed and delivers the basis on which standard operating procedures and practices rest	(Anku-Tsede, 2014)
Finance (B4)	Budget (C11)	Insufficient funds affect the continuity of operations and tasks.	(Thomas, 2008)
	Funding (C12)	The historical decline in funding is the major challenge faced by NGOs.	(Thomas, 2008)
	Donations (C13)	NGOs are required to re-align their urgencies with donor benefits in order to compete for donations.	(Thomas, 2008)
HR Practices (B5)	Recruitment (C14)	It is important to train employees with required skills and capabilities in today's modest situation for the sake of increasing efficiency of NGOs.	(Kadiresan, 2015)
	Training/Development (C15)	Employees should continuously improve themselves by latest training and education.	(Rothwell, Jackson, Ressler, Jones, & Brower, 2015)
	Employee Engagement (C16)	The performance of organization improves through employee engagement.	(Tensay, & Singh, 2020)
Remuneration (B6)	Workload (C17)	High workload is negatively associated with engagement, dedication, interest and stamina.	(Timms, Graham, & Cottrell, 2007)
	Employee motivation (C18)	To achieve higher performance of employees, Additional allowances enhance the motivation of employees.	(Dobre, 2013)
	Turnover rate (C19)	Due to higher turnover rate, organizations face greater loss in productivity and performance.	(Park & Min, 2020)
Organizational Commitment (B7)	Employee Behavior (C20)	Work behaviors are associated to organizational performance. It increased organizational commitment and involvement.	(Gould-Williams & Mohamed, 2010; Tremblay et al., 2010; Wright et al., 2003)
	Teamwork (C21)	Employees need to be team members and help each other for the progress of organizations.	(Ozduran & Tanova, 2017)
	Employee Honesty (C22)	The conservative economic prototype undertakes that maximization of wealth, self-centered homo-economic is authentic individual in so far as the physical rewards for honesty compensate the motivations.	(Rosenbaum et al., 2014)

3. Methodology

This research is based on interpretivism. The research approach is inductive and survey method is used to gather qualitative information. Seven susceptible factors have been identified from literature and expert's opinion which were further categorized into twenty two sub-factors in order to deal with the issue of declining performance of non-

governmental organizations in greater detail. The *twelve* members' panel of experts is recruited to collect data. For a homogeneous type of groups, minimum of 15-20 members are required in panel, whereas for heterogeneous groups, 5-10 members are required (Clayton, 1997; Khan & Khan, 2013). However, the ISM is workable technique with only 1-2 experts (Shen et al., 2016) or only 5 experts (Sushil, 2017). The ISM is also workable with as much as 80 elements (Li et al., 2019). One-on-one, face-to-face discussion sessions with experts were conducted to obtain their opinions on factors' relevance, importance, and inclusivity in the model (Li & Yang, 2014). To analyze qualitative data, expert elicitation is the best option (Avinash et al., 2018; Dwivedi et al., 2017; Majumdar & Sinha, 2019). This study has 3 phases of discussion of expert elicitation by means of direct (one-to-one), frontal (face-to-face), and detailed discussion sessions. During the first phase, several rounds of discussions were conducted to introduce the factors of NGOs to the experts. In the second phase, the importance of *twenty-two* susceptibility factors was discussed. During the third phase, the experts marked relationship between the factors. For the purpose of ranking and creating hierarchal model in order to better understand the susceptibility factors and inter relationship among them, the classical approach interpretive structural modeling (ISM) is used. The ISM has wide range of applications (Sushil, 2017; Warfield, 1973; Warfield, 1974). It establishes relationship among factors, useful to analyze interaction among them, which most of the statistical techniques do not analyze (Chidambaranathan et al., 2009). The workflow process diagram for the whole process of research is shown in figure 1.

3.1. Interpretive Structural Modeling (ISM)

The typical classical steps (Attri et al., 2013; Thakkar et al., 2008; Warfield, 1973) to use ISM are as: (i) Identify factor set, (ii) Construct Structural Self-Interaction Matrix (SSIM, Table 2), (iii) Construct Initial Reachability Matrix (Table 3), (iv) Construct Final Reachability Matrix (Table 4), (v) Construct Level Partitioning (Table 5-14) and (vi) Drawing Diagram (Figure 2).

Figure 1: Process Flow Chart of Research Process

Table 2: Structural Self-Interaction Matrix (SSIM)

Sr.	Factors	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	2	2	
1	Proactive Approach	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	A	0	0	V	V	V	0	0	0	A	0	0	0	0	
2	Responsibility		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	V	0	X	0	A	0	0
3	Appreciation/Reward			0	V	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	V	0	0	0	A
4	Politics				0	V	0	0	V	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
5	Dictatorship					0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
6	Advance & Latest Technology						0	X	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	V	0	0	V	0	0	0
7	Technology Experts							0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	V	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
8	Executive Body								0	V	V	V	V	V	V	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
9	Rules & Regulations									0	0	0	0	X	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
10	Organizational Structure										0	0	0	V	0	A	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11	Budget											0	0	V	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
12	Funding												0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
13	Donations													0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
14	Recruitment														0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
15	Training/Development															0	0	V	0	V	0	0	0
16	Employee Engagement																X	0	A	A	A	A	A
17	Workload																	0	V	0	0	0	0
18	Employee Motivation																		0	A	0	0	0
19	Turnover Rate																			0	0	0	0
20	Employee Behavior																				0	V	0
21	Teamwork																					A	0
22	Employee Honesty																						0

Table 3: Initial Reachability Matrix

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	
1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
3	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
4	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
6	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
7	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
8	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
9	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
10	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
12	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
13	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
14	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
15	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0
16	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
17	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
18	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
19	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
20	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
21	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
22	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0

Table 4: Final Reachability Matrix

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	
1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1*	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1*	0	0	0	0	0	1	1*	1	0	0	0	0	0
3	0	1*	1	1	1*	0	0	1*	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
4	1*	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	1*	1*	1*	1*	1*	1*	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
5	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
6	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	1*	0	0	0	0	1*	1	1*	0	1	0	0	0	0
7	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1*	0	1*	1*	1*	0	0	0	0
8	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
9	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
10	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1*	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1*	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
12	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

13	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
14	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
15	0	1*	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1*	0	1	0	1	0	1*
16	1*	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1*	0	1	1	0	1*	0	0	0
17	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1*	1*	1*	1*	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	0
18	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1*	0	1	0	0	0	0
19	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1*	0	0	0	0	0	1	1*	0	1	0	0	0
20	0	1	1*	0	0	0	0	0	0	1*	0	0	0	0	0	1	1*	1	0	1	1*	1
21	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1*	0	0	0	0	0	1	1*	0	0	0	1	0
22	0	0	1	1*	0	0	0	0	0	1*	0	0	0	0	0	1	1*	1*	0	0	1	1

Table 5: Level Partitioning-Level I

Factor	Reachability Set	Antecedence Set	Intersection Set	Level
1	1,11,12,13,14	1,4,8,16,17	1	
2	2,10,16,17,18	2,3,15,18,20	2,18	
3	2,3,4,5,8,18	3,20,22	3	
4	1,4,5,8,9,10,11,12,13,14	3,4,22	4	
5	5	3,4,5	5	I
6	6,7,10,15,16,17,19	6,7	6,7	
7	6,7,15,16,18,19,20	6,7	6,7	
8	1,8,9,10,11,12,13,14	3,4,8	8	
9	9,14	4,8,9,10,11,14	9,14	I
10	9,10,14	2,4,6,8,10,16,17,19,20,21,22	10	
11	9,11,14	1,4,8,11,17	11	
12	12	1,4,8,12,17	12	I
13	13	1,4,8,13,17	13	I
14	9,14	1,4,8,9,10,11,14,16	9,14	I
15	2,15,16,18,20,22	6,7,15	15	
16	1,10,14,16,17,19	2,6,7,15,16,17,18,19,20,21,22	16,17,19	
17	1,10,11,12,13,16,17,19	2,6,16,17,19,20,21,22	16,17,19	
18	2,16,18	2,3,7,15,18,20,22	2,18	
19	10,16,17,19	6,7,16,17,19	16,17,19	
20	2,3,10,16,17,18,20,21,22	7,15,20	20	
21	10,16,17,21	20,21,22	21	
22	3,4,10,16,17,18,21,22	15,20,22	22	

Table 6: Level Partitioning-Level II

Factor	Reachability Set	Antecedence Set	Intersection Set	Level
1	1,11	1,4,8,16,17	1	
2	2,10,16,17,18	2,3,15,18,20	2,18	
3	2,3,4,8,18	3,20,22	3	
4	1,4,8,10,11	3,4,22	4	
6	6,7,10,15,16,17,19	6,7	6,7	
7	6,7,15,16,18,19,20	6,7	6,7	
8	1,8,10,11	3,4,8	8	
10	10	2,4,6,8,10,16,17,19,20,21,22	10	II
11	11	1,4,8,11,17	11	II
15	2,15,16,18,20,22	6,7,15	15	
16	1,10,16,17,19	2,6,7,15,16,17,18,19,20,21,22	16,17,19	
17	1,10,11,16,17,19	2,6,16,17,19,20,21,22	16,17,19	
18	2,16,18	2,3,7,15,18,20,22	2,18	
19	10,16,17,19	6,7,16,17,19	16,17,19	
20	2,3,10,16,17,18,20,21,22	7,15,20	20	
21	10,16,17,21	20,21,22	21	
22	3,4,10,16,17,18,21,22	15,20,22	22	

Table 7: Level Partitioning-Level III

Factor	Reachability Set	Antecedence Set	Intersection Set	Level
1	1	1,4,8,16,17	1	III
2	2,16,17,18	2,3,15,18,20	2,18	
3	2,3,4,8,18	3,20,22	3	
4	1,4,8	3,4,22	4	
6	6,7,15,16,17,19	6,7	6,7	
7	6,7,15,16,18,19,20	6,7	6,7	
8	1,8	3,4,8	8	
15	2,15,16,18,20,22	6,7,15	15	
16	1,16,17,19	2,6,7,15,16,17,18,19,20,21,22	16,17,19	
17	1,16,17,19	2,6,16,17,19,20,21,22	16,17,19	
18	2,16,18	2,3,7,15,18,20,22	2,18	
19	16,17,19	6,7,16,17,19	16,17,19	

20	2,3,16,17,18,20,21,22	7,15,20	20
21	16,17,21	20,21,22	21
22	3,4,16,17,18,21,22	15,20,22	22

Table 8: Level Partitioning-Level IV

Factor	Reachability Set	Antecedence Set	Intersection Set	Level
2	2,16,17,18	2,3,15,18,20	2,18	
3	2,3,4,8,18	3,20,22	3	
4	4,8	3,4,22	4	
6	6,7,15,16,17,19	6,7	6,7	
7	6,7,15,16,18,19,20	6,7	6,7	
8	8	3,4,8	8	IV
15	2,15,16,18,20,22	6,7,15	15	
16	16,17,19	2,6,7,15,16,17,18,19,20,21,22	16,17,19	IV
17	16,17,19	2,6,16,17,19,20,21,22	16,17,19	IV
18	2,16,18	2,3,7,15,18,20,22	2,18	
19	16,17,19	6,7,16,17,19	16,17,19	IV
20	2,3,16,17,18,20,21,22	7,15,20	20	
21	16,17,21	20,21,22	21	
22	3,4,16,17,18,21,22	15,20,22	22	

Table 9: Level Partitioning-Level V

Factor	Reachability Set	Antecedence Set	Intersection Set	Level
2	2,18	2,3,15,18,20	2,18	V
3	2,3,4,18	3,20,22	3	
4	4	3,4,22	4	V
6	6,7,15	6,7	6,7	
7	6,7,15,18,20	6,7	6,7	
15	2,15,18,20,22	6,7,15	15	
18	2,18	2,3,7,15,18,20,22	2,18	V
20	2,3,18,20,21,22	7,15,20	20	
21	21	20,21,22	21	V
22	3,4,18,21,22	15,20,22	22	

Table 10: Level Partitioning-Level VI

Factor	Reachability Set	Antecedence Set	Intersection Set	Level
3	3	3,20,22	3	VI
6	6,7,15	6,7	6,7	
7	6,7,15,20	6,7	6,7	
15	15,20,22	6,7,15	15	
20	3,20,22	7,15,20	20	
22	3,22	15,20,22	22	

Table 11: Level Partitioning-Level VII

Factor	Reachability Set	Antecedence Set	Intersection Set	Level
6	6,7,15	6,7	6,7	
7	6,7,15,20	6,7	6,7	
15	15,20,22	6,7,15	15	
20	20,22	7,15,20	20	
22	22	15,20,22	22	VII

Table 12: Level Partitioning-Level VIII

Factor	Reachability Set	Antecedence Set	Intersection Set	Level
6	6,7,15	6,7	6,7	
7	6,7,15,20	6,7	6,7	
15	15,20	6,7,15	15	
20	20	7,15,20	20	VIII

Table 13: Level Partitioning-Level IX

Factor	Reachability Set	Antecedence Set	Intersection Set	Level
6	6,7,15	6,7	6,7	
7	6,7,15	6,7	6,7	
15	15	6,7,15	15	IX

Table 14: Level Partitioning-Level X

Factor	Reachability Set	Antecedence Set	Intersection Set	Level
6	6,7	6,7	6,7	X
7	6,7	6,7	6,7	X

Figure 2: An ISM Model- Susceptible Performance Factors of NGOs in Pakistan

3.2. Conical Matrix

The dependence/independence powers are shown in conical matrix (Figure 2). Conical matrix shows the linkages of all factors that are dependent and independent. Dependent factors are those factors which have feeble driving power and strong dependence power. The factors which have weak dependence power and strong driving power are independent power.

It is observed that factors (5), (9), (12), (13) and (14) are on *Level I*. Factors (10) and (11) are on *Level II* and factor (1) is on *Level III*. Factor (8), (16), (17) and (19) are on *Level IV* and Factors (2), (4), (18) and (21) are on *Level V*. Factor (3) is *Level VI* and factor (22) is on *level VII*. Factor (20) is on *level VIII*, (15) on *Level IX* and (6) & (7) are on *Level X*.

It can be seen, that MICMAC (shown in Figure 3) have presented Employee Engagement C16 in dependent section and C8 in Independent section respectively and rest of the variables in autonomous section.

Driving	10									
	9									
	8	C8	Independent					Linkage		
	7									
	6									
	5	C20								
	4	C6, C17, C22	C1	Autonomous				Dependent		
	3	C3,C4,C7, C15	C2					C16		
	2	C21	C9,C10,C11, C19		C14, C18					
	1	C5	C12,V13							
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Dependence										

Figure 3: MICMAC Diagram

Table 15: Summary of ISM and MICMAC

No	Variables	Dependence	Driving	Cluster	Level
1	C1	3	4	Autonomous	III
2	C2	3	3	Autonomous	IV
3	C3	2	3	Autonomous	VI
4	C4	2	3	Autonomous	V
5	C5	2	1	Autonomous	I
6	C6	2	4	Autonomous	X
7	C7	2	3	Autonomous	X
8	C8	2	8	Independent	IV
9	C9	3	2	Autonomous	I
10	C10	3	2	Autonomous	II
11	C11	3	2	Autonomous	II
12	C12	3	1	Autonomous	I
13	C13	3	1	Autonomous	I
14	C14	5	2	Autonomous	I
15	C15	2	3	Autonomous	IX
16	C16	8	3	Dependent	IV
17	C17	2	4	Autonomous	IV
18	C18	5	2	Autonomous	V
19	C19	3	2	Autonomous	IV
20	C20	2	5	Autonomous	VIII
21	C21	2	2	Autonomous	V
22	C22	2	4	Autonomous	VII

4. Results & Discussion

4.1. Discussion about ISM Analysis

Figure 2 describes all the susceptibility factors into ten hierarchical levels.

Level I: Dictatorship, funding, donations, rules & regulations and recruitment are mapped on the top-level factors for sustainable development of NGOs'. Hiring should be clean and wise, not on bases of reference.

Level II: Organizational structure and budget are linked with Proactive Approach. A Strong organizational structure and budget are proactive approaches for building strong mechanism of hiring employees on merit.

Level III: Proactive approach is placed on third level. Organizational structure gets strong through proactive measures.

Level IV: Executive body, employee engagement, workload and turnover rate are placed on level IV. Executive body can take proactive measures to play its role in designing an effective organizational structure to deal with dictatorship

issues. In many NGOs', executive body is responsible to take proactive decisions, making policies and implementing rules & regulations.

Level V: politics, responsibility, employee motivation and teamwork are on *level V*.

Level VI: Appreciation rewards fall on *level VI*. Appreciation rewards are provided on the basis of employee honesty and leads to job engagement that further proactively contribute to forming rules and regulations for organizational processes.

Level VII: Employee honesty is placed on *level VII*. Employee motivation, employee engagement and responsibility are linked with employee behavior.

Level VIII: Employee behavior is placed on *level VIII*. If an Employee is honest, he will work well and get appreciation, which leads to positive change in Employee Behavior. Appreciation can be in any form e.g., bonus, cash, gifts, rewards, praise. Appreciation reward is a key source for the employee motivation.

Level IX: Training & development is placed on *level IX*. Employees' behaviour can be changed through training & development. Employees get motivated through training. And responsibility is also linked with employee engagement which keeps them motivated.

Level X: advance & latest technology and technology experts. Technology experts are also needed to harness the benefits of advance technology. They both are interlinked in the model. The interest of employees increases due to advance technology and hence turnover rate reduces.

4.2. Discussion about MICMAC Analysis

MICMAC enhances the reliability and validity of the ISM model. MICMAC presents factors as independent, dependent, linkage and autonomous variables. In current study's MICMAC, C16 appeared as dependent and C8 as Independent variables respectively and rest of the variables appeared in autonomous section.

The objective of conducting this research is to understand the susceptibility factors to enhance and sustainable performance of NGOs. As per the ISM results, Teamwork, rules & regulations and recruitment occupy *Level I*, therefore, the least critical factors. This study is very helpful for NGOs as well as other organizations of the same purpose and structure. Analysis through ISM model is very beneficial especially for stakeholders e.g., administrators of NGOs of Pakistan, donors, beneficiaries and volunteers and society.

The ISM model is based on experts' opinion. It may be biased. NGOs' can use this hierarchical model in their operating system to sustain performance, productivity and growth. It defines how one variable derives/influence from/to other variables and how to control other variables to remove inconsistencies.

4.3. Discussion about contribution of the study

Unfortunately, previous researchers did not focus onto exploring factors that have caused failure of NGOs in Pakistan. This study is first of its nature to address issues of NGOs. The classical technique of ISM is used to highlight most critical factors, which can be controlled to overcome the issue and put the NGOs of Pakistan on the path of sustainable development. Since, very limited literature is available in the context of the study, so, getting first-hand information from the experts of the field and converting it to useful hierarchal model is the foundation for further research. The potential research may use other qualitative/quantitative techniques to corroborate the results of this study and further contribute to the phenomenon under study.

4.4. Discussion about limitations of the study

Though this study is fruitful to its stakeholders, it is not without limitations. Since it is based on researchers' personal observation of literature and experts' opinion, some of the factors that are commensurate to study in the context of the current phenomenon of interest might have not been covered in this study. Further, this study has proposed a structural model that is open to verification using quantitative techniques which is not covered in this study. The interested readers and researcher might test this model through quantitative techniques such as SEM, GRA, TOPSIS and Fuzzy-TOPSIS etc. Finally, the research and its findings are applicable in Pakistan only in the context of non-government organizations, the researchers might replicate and corroborate it for other cultures/societies/organizations/countries and/or regions.

5. Conclusion

Non-government organizations are not for profit making organizations. They help to empower and bring betterment in our societies. Government should take necessary steps for the continuous survival of NGOs' because they are facing very serious issues in their operations. The susceptibility factors are selected after the background study and the induction of experts. ISM techniques are three decades matured, their merits of elasticity and strength to make broad applications in many areas. As per the formation and linkages of ISM model, dictatorship, funding, donations, rules & regulations and recruitment are listed in the first level. In the second level, organizational structure and budget affects to recruitment employees, process of making rules and regulations and acquiring donations. The executive body is responsible to take proactive approach for the performance of organizations. Proactive strategies should be under observation to solve the issues of budget, funding, and donations. Workload increases turnover rate, it can be handled

with the training and development, appreciation rewards. Training/Development, appreciation, and responsibility increase the employee motivation that enhances job engagement. Employee's behaviour is changed through training & development to make them honest towards organization and its objectives. The honest employees put more efforts and contribute to achieving organizational mission and vision. If organization rewards honest employees for their good behaviour, their job motivation and hence job engagement enhances, which is irreplaceable asset for any company. The structural model proposed by researchers will be a useful guide to practitioners in designing organizational structure that is commensurate to attract a good amount of funding necessary to run the affairs of NGOs and put them on the path of sustainable development.

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